

GLOSSARY

Section “General questions about the company”

Intelligent Transportation system (ITS) — the advanced applications which, without embodying intelligence as such, aim to provide innovative services relating to different modes of transport and traffic management and enable various users to be better informed and make safer, more coordinated and ‘smarter’ use of transport networks.

Section "Organisation"

Heterogeneous network — a network connecting computers and other devices with different operating systems and/or protocols.

Principles of data minimisation — data controllers should collect only the personal data they really need and should keep it only for as long as they need it.

Interoperability — a characteristic of a product or system to work with other products or systems.

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 2"

Anonymous authentication — the process of confirming a user's right to access a webpage or other service. Unlike traditional authentication, which may require credentials such as a username and password, anonymous authentication allows users to log in to the system without exposing their actual identity.

Secret-sharing — methods for distributing a secret among a group, in such a way that no individual holds any intelligible information about the secret, but when a sufficient number of individuals combine their 'shares', the secret may be reconstructed.

Multi-party computation — methods for parties to jointly compute a function over their inputs while keeping those inputs private.

Attribute-based credentials — an authorization model that evaluates attributes (or characteristics), rather than roles, to determine access.

RFID authentication — uses electromagnetic fields to automatically identify and track tags attached to objects.

Public key infrastructure — a set of roles, policies, hardware, software and procedures needed to create, manage, distribute, use, store and revoke digital certificates and manage public-key encryption.

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 3"

Token-based payment — payments in which the PAN is substituted by a token while performing a payment transaction. With tokenized payments, the PAN is not transmitted during the transaction, making the payment more secure.

Anonymous Payment — any system that can be used to pay for goods and services in which the buyer shares little or no information about themselves with the seller.

Automated payment using smart contract — using blockchain and smart contracts which automatically initiate the transaction of money deduction once the set conditions are met. The transaction data is stored in blockchain.

Private information retrieval — a protocol that allows a user to retrieve an item from a server in possession of a database without revealing which item is retrieved.

Hashmap storing of locations — storing locations grouped or joined by some common attribute.

Blind signature — a form of digital signature in which the content of a message is disguised (blinded) before it is signed.

Anonymous reservation — reservation of the parking or ticket issuance in a way that the document itself does not contain any information about the reservation/ticket receiver's real identity.

Presenting proof-of-knowledge — a method by which one party (the prover) can prove to another party (the verifier) that a given statement is true while the prover avoids conveying any additional information apart from the fact that the statement is indeed true.

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 4"

Privacy by design — an approach to systems engineering that calls for privacy to be taken into account throughout the whole engineering process.

Data minimisation — data controllers should collect only the personal data they really need and should keep it only for as long as they need it.

Secure programming — the practice of developing software in such a way that guards against the accidental introduction of security vulnerabilities.

Intrusion detection system — a device or software application that monitors a network or systems for malicious activity or policy violations.

Security incident and event management systems (SEIM) — the process of identifying, monitoring, recording and analyzing security events or incidents within a real-time IT environment.

Behavioural analytics system — using machine learning, artificial intelligence, big data, and analytics to identify malicious behavior by analyzing differences in normal, everyday activities.